

HOMOGENIZATION METHOD TO PREDICT THREE-DIMENSIONAL PERMEABILITIES CONSIDERING MICRO-MACRO AND SOLID-FLUID INTERACTIONS

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SUMMARY: Formulation of the homogenization for solid-fluid mixture is presented. The possibility of applying this newly developed homogenization method to the liquid molding analysis has been investigated. Firstly, the three-dimensional anisotropic permeabilities were calculated for arbitrary microstructures. Especially for the uni-directional fiber arrangement, the computational results and conventional theoretical results were compared. For both square arrangement and hexagonal one, the computational results agreed very well with the theoretical prediction. Then the developed homogenization method was applied to the prediction of the permeability of knitted fabric composite material. Three-dimensionally anisotropic permeabilities were obtained. Secondly, macroscopic behaviors of both solid deformation and flow velocity (averaged Darcy's velocity) have been simulated.

KEYWORDS: Microstructure, FRP, Moulding, Permeability, Homogenization method

INTRODUCTION

The homogenization method is a mathematical theory for numerical analysis of the heterogeneous media [1-3]. This method can well describe the micro-macro coupled behaviors. The authors have applied so far this method to the stress analysis of textile fabric composite materials [4-6] and sandwich panel [7]. Recently, one of the authors has presented a new formulation of the homogenization for solid-fluid mixture [8,9] in the field of soil mechanics or biomechanics. In this study, above developed homogenization method is applied to the prediction of three-dimensional anisotropic permeabilities and the liquid molding analysis of composite materials.

There have been many studies on the liquid molding process simulation [10-13]. Generally the Darcy's law is used. Then, the preliminary experiment is required to measure the permeability. For an uni-directional fiber reinforcement system, Kozeny-Carman equation, analytical equation [14], self-consistent method and numerical approach [12,13] have been studied to predict the permeability. We can find, however, no literature on the prediction of permeability for other complex fiber system. Some experimental works are presented for woven fabrics, cross mat and chopped strand mat to determine the Kozeny constant. However, many difficulties lie in the experiment such as the problem of edge flow effect [15]. Also the measurement of three-dimensional permeabilities is a difficult problem [16]. On the contrary, the homogenization method that can calculate the three-dimensional anisotropic permeability for arbitrary microstructure is very useful. This method can also solve the problems for shear-deformed fiber tows [17] or perturbation effects of fiber arrangement [18].

The most notable feature of the homogenization method is the consideration of macro-micro coupling effects. Hence, the macroscopic behaviors of both solid and fluid phases are also analyzed.

FORMULATION

Suppose two scales, i.e., macroscale \mathbf{x} and microscale \mathbf{y} as shown in Fig.1. Define the scale ratio $\varepsilon = \ell/L$, where L and ℓ are the representative dimensions of macro- and microscales, respectively. The (macroscopic) body is supposed to be consistent of periodic array of microscopic unit cells. To consider the coupling effects of macro-micro behaviors, physical quantities are expanded asymptotically using macroscopic quantities and microscopic ones. Then, the displacements, pressure and velocities can be expressed as follows [8,9].

Fig. 1: Definition of macroscale and microscale

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_i^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) &= u_i^0(\mathbf{x}, t) + \varepsilon u_i^1(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) + \dots \\
 p^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) &= p^0(\mathbf{x}, t) + \varepsilon p^1(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) + \dots \\
 v_i^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) &= v_i^0(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) + \varepsilon v_i^1(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) + \dots
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The governing equation for a solid-fluid mixture can be written as follows.

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}^\varepsilon}{\partial x_j} + \rho^\varepsilon f_i = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega^\varepsilon \tag{2}$$

The constitutive equations for solid phase and Newtonian fluid phase with Stoke's condition can be simply described as

$$\sigma_{ij}^\varepsilon = b_{ijkh}^\varepsilon \varepsilon_{kh}(\mathbf{u}^\varepsilon) + c_{ijkh}^\varepsilon \varepsilon_{kh} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}^\varepsilon}{\partial t} \right) \quad (3)$$

where

$$c_{ijkh}^\varepsilon = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{in } \Omega_\varepsilon^s \\ 2\mu^{*\varepsilon} \left(\delta_{ik} \delta_{jh} - \frac{1}{3} \delta_{ij} \delta_{kh} \right) & \text{in } \Omega_\varepsilon^f \end{cases}$$

$$b_{ijkh}^\varepsilon = \begin{cases} E_{ijkh} & \text{in } \Omega_\varepsilon^s \\ \frac{1}{3} K^f \delta_{ij} \delta_{kh} & \text{in } \Omega_\varepsilon^f \end{cases}$$

and the superscripts s and f denote solid and fluid phases, respectively. Next, to consider the coupling effects of solid and fluid phases, suppose that the deformation of solid phase and the pressure of fluid phase are affected with each other. This can be expressed as follows.

$$p^\varepsilon \delta_{ij} n_j^f = E_{ijlm} \frac{\partial u_l^\varepsilon}{\partial x_m} n_j^s \quad \text{on } \Sigma \quad (4)$$

Also suppose that the fluid flows in and out from the microscopic unit cell. That is, the mass conservation of the fluid is considered.

Then the homogenization method decouples the complex coupled problem into micro- and macroscopic sub-problems.

At the microscale, firstly, we obtain the following microscopic equation for fluid phase.

$$\mu \int_{Y_f} D \frac{\partial \kappa_i^k}{\partial y_j} \frac{\partial W_i}{\partial y_j} dy = \int_{Y_f} W_k dy \quad \forall W_i \quad (5)$$

Here κ_i^k is the characteristic velocity function which can describe the characteristics of microscopic flow field. D denotes the properties of the fluid. After solving this characteristic velocity function, the homogenized anisotropic permeability can be calculated by Eq.(6) three-dimensionally.

$$K_{ik} \equiv \langle \kappa_i^k \rangle \quad (6)$$

The so-called Darcy's law is then generalized as follows.

$$V_i \equiv \langle v_i^0 \rangle = \frac{\partial u_i^0(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial t} - K_{ik} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_k} \quad (7)$$

where

$$v_i^0(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) = \frac{\partial u_i^0(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial t} + \left(\rho_f f_k - \frac{\partial p^0}{\partial x_k}(\mathbf{x}, t) \right) \kappa_i^k(\mathbf{y})$$

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_k} \equiv -\rho_f f_k + \frac{\partial p^0}{\partial x_k}(\mathbf{x}, t)$$

For solid phase at the microscale, we obtain the following microscopic equation.

$$\int_{Y_s} E_{ijlm} \frac{\partial \chi_l^{kh}}{\partial y_m} \frac{\partial w_i^1}{\partial y_j} dy = \int_{Y_s} E_{ijkh} \frac{\partial w_i^1}{\partial y_j} dy \quad \forall w_i^1 \quad (8)$$

Here, χ_l^{kh} is the characteristic deformation of the solid phase. The homogenized anisotropic stress-strain tensor can be calculated as follows.

$$E_{ijkh}^H = \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_{Y_s} \left(E_{ijkh} - E_{ijlm} \frac{\partial \chi_l^{kh}}{\partial y_m} \right) dy \quad (9)$$

Another characteristic deformation due to the pressure of the fluid phase can be obtained by solving the next microscopic equation.

$$\int_{Y_s} E_{ijlm} \frac{\partial \phi_l}{\partial y_m} \frac{\partial w_i^1}{\partial y_j} dy = \int_{Y_s} \frac{\partial w_i^1}{\partial y_i} dy \quad \forall w_i^1 \quad (10)$$

Then the homogenized elastic tensor associated with the pressure of the fluid phase can be defined as follows.

$$Q_{ij}^H = \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_{Y_s} E_{ijlm} \frac{\partial \phi_l}{\partial y_m} dy \quad (11)$$

From above, the microscopic deformation can be expressed as follows using two types of characteristic deformation.

$$u_i^1(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) = -\chi_i^{kh}(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial u_k^0}{\partial x_h}(\mathbf{x}, t) - \phi_i(\mathbf{y}) p^0(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (12)$$

The decoupled macroscopic equations are as follows. The second equation (14) denotes the conservation of mass.

$$\int_{\Omega} E_{ijkh}^H \frac{\partial u_k^0}{\partial x_h} \frac{\partial w_i^0}{\partial x_j} dx - \int_{\Omega} p^0 Q_{ij}^H \frac{\partial w_i^0}{\partial x_j} dx = \int_{\Omega} f_i^{sH} w_i^0 dx + \int_{\Gamma_f} \hat{t}_i w ds \quad \forall w_i^0 \quad (13)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\frac{\partial u_i^0}{\partial t} \right) \theta dx + \int_{\Omega} K_{ik} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x_i} dx + \int_{\Gamma_u} \hat{q} \theta ds = 0 \quad \forall \theta \quad (14)$$

where

$$f_i^{SH} = \frac{|Y_s|}{|Y|} \rho_s f$$

Above equations can be solved numerically by the finite element method (FEM). Note that the microscopic equations are solved with periodic conditions put on the unit cell.

MICROSCOPIC ANALYSIS AND THE PREDICTION OF PERMEABILITY

Suppose a uni-directional fiber reinforced composite material. Its microstructure is modeled as Fig.2. Two cases of fiber array, i.e., square array and hexagonal one, are considered as shown in Fig.2. The material properties used for the analysis is in Table 1. Based on the formulation in the previous chapter, the homogenized permeabilities are calculated. The transverse permeability is plotted in Fig.3. The horizontal axis indicates the fiber volume fraction, and the vertical one indicates the calculated permeability divided by the square root of the fiber radius.

Table 1: Material properties

	Young's modulus	Poisson's ratio	Viscosity
Solid	85 GPa	0.22	$10^8 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$
Fluid	$1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ GPa}$	0.30	$10^{-3} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$

solid phase

fluid phase

(a) Square array

solid phase

fluid phase

(b) Hexagonal array

Fig. 2: Microstructure model of uni-directional fiber reinforced composite material

Fig. 3: Calculated transverse permeability of uni-directional fiber reinforced composite material and the comparison with theoretical methods

To verify the accuracy of the predicted permeability, computational results were compared with the conventional theoretical predictions. Most commonly used prediction is the Kozeny-Carman equation (15).

$$S_x = \frac{r_f^2 (1 - V_f)^3}{4s_x V_f^2} \quad (15)$$

where

r_f : fiber radius

s_x : material constants which should be obtained experimentally

V_f : fiber volume fraction

The material constants s_x in Eq.(15) must be obtained prior to the calculation by experiment. In the comparison, $s_x=11.0$ is used for uni-directional fiber arrangement after Ref.[10]. Many modifications have been carried out based on the Kozeny-Carman equation. The following equation was presented by Gebart in 1992 [14].

$$S_x = C_1 \left(\sqrt{\frac{V_{f \max}}{V_f}} - 1 \right)^2 r_f^2 \quad (16)$$

Table 2: Constants in the equation by Gebart

Fiber Arrangement	C_1	$V_{f \max}$
Square	$\frac{16}{9\pi\sqrt{2}}$	$\frac{\pi}{4}$
Hexagonal	$\frac{16}{9\pi\sqrt{6}}$	$\frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{3}}$

The constants in Eq.(16) are given as shown in Table 2. In Eq.(16) and Table 2, the difference between the square arrangement and hexagonal arrangement of uni-directional fibers are expressed. Both the computational and theoretical results are plotted in Fig.3. The computational results agreed very well with the equation by Gebart. The Kozeny-Carman equation provided the intermediate prediction close to the results for the case of hexagonal arrangement. From this numerical test, the developed homogenization method has been found to be effective and reliable.

Nextly, the three-dimensional anisotropic permeabilities were calculated for a knitted fabric composite material. This composite material has very complicated microstructure. Fig.4 shows the microstructure model of a jersey weft knitted fabric composite laminate. Following is the calculated permeability matrix.

Fig. 4: Microstructure model of jersey knitted fabric composite laminate

$$K = \begin{bmatrix} 8.18 \times 10^{-3} & 0 & 0 \\ & 5.76 \times 10^{-3} & 0 \\ \text{sym.} & & 3.44 \times 10^{-3} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{m}^2 / \text{Pa} \cdot \text{s}) \quad (17)$$

This result implies that the homogenization method is applicable to any kinds of composite materials. Furthermore, it is more useful than any other computational methods such as Refs.[10-13], because the homogenization method using the periodicity boundary conditions requires only one period of microstructure model. Also this method provides very reliable prediction of three-dimensional permeabilities, because the edge flow effect is removed which we often encounter in experiment [15].

MICRO-MACRO COUPLED ANALYSIS

Suppose a hypothetical porous microstructure saturated with fluid as shown in Fig.5. The homogenized properties are calculated as shown in Table 3. Suppose a macroscopic domain

that consists of periodic array of this hypothetical microstructure as shown in Fig.6. Using the calculated homogenized properties in Table 3, macroscopic analysis is possible for arbitrary boundary condition. In this case, load is applied partially on the top surface. Symmetry is assumed on the left side of the domain. On the right side of the domain, the deformation is fixed and the fluid can be permeable. Macroscopic deformation is shown in Fig.6. Averaged flow velocity and pressure are also analyzed. In the case of cell model A, both deformation and velocity are larger than the case of cell model B. This result is quite reasonable considering the microstructure and the homogenized properties.

Table 3: Calculated homogenized properties

	Young's modulus (GPa)	Shear modulus (GPa)	Poisson's ratio	Homogenized pressure coefficient (GPa)	Permeability (m ² /Pa·s)
Model A	10.7	9.19×10 ⁻¹	7.76×10 ⁻²	1.76×10 ⁻¹	9.59×10 ⁻³
Model B	47.7	14.8	1.71×10 ⁻¹	2.64×10 ⁻¹	4.52×10 ⁻⁴

Fig. 5: Microstructure model for micro-macro coupled analysis

Fig. 6: Computational result of macroscopic deformation

CONCLUSIONS

The formulation of the homogenization method for solid-fluid mixture is briefly described, and some demonstrative numerical examples are shown.

For the prediction of anisotropic three-dimensional permeabilities, this method is very effective, because arbitrary and complex microstructure can be analyzed. The characteristic functions are expected to lead to the design of microstructures. Also some demonstrative macroscopic analyses were shown. As one of the future works, the microscopic behaviors can be evaluated at any point in the macroscopic domain. This will lead to the prediction of ill impregnation.

Microstructure-based process simulation is a novel technique, and it can be an effective tool for the design of material, structure and process. Also the authors are now building up a computational method for deep-drawing simulation considering the large deformation of the microstructure [19].

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